

Acknowledgement

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Studies on Hydroxamic Acids : Part I Separation and Gravimetric Determination of Barium using N-m-Tolyl-m-Nitrobenzohydro- xamic Acid

P. C. VERMA, Y. K. AGRAWAL* & P. V. KHADIKAR**

Department of Chemistry, Government Polytechnic,
Ujjain (M.P.)

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THE hydroxamic acids are found useful reagents for carrying out gravimetry¹⁻⁵, spectrophotometry⁶⁻⁹ and for other analytical techniques^{10,11}. Some methods for gravimetric determination of barium were reported earlier¹²⁻¹⁴. But no such systematic method has so far been reported for separation and gravimetric determination of barium. This method is most suitable for the separation and gravimetric determination of barium. The N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid reacts with barium chloride solution to give a complete precipitation of barium in presence of Ag⁺, Mn⁺², Cu⁺², Ni⁺², Cd⁺², Zn⁺², Hg⁺², Pd⁺², Be⁺², Ga⁺³, Sb⁺³, As⁺³, Bi⁺³, Ti⁺⁴, Zr⁺⁴, V⁺⁵, Mo⁺⁶ and UO₂⁺², Pr⁺³, Nd⁺³ and Sm⁺³ at pH 2.5-3.0, adjusted by hydrochloric acid and ammonium hydroxide. The purity of the complex was checked by I.R., U.V. and elemental analysis.

Experimental

Chemicals :

All the chemicals used were of G.R. and AnalaR grades of E. Merck and B.D.H., respectively unless otherwise stated.

Reagents :

The aqueous stock solution of barium chloride was prepared by dissolving 1 g of barium chloride

* To whom correspondence should be made : Health Physics Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Bombay-400085.

** School of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain (M.P.), India.

in a litre of double distilled water. The contents of barium were determined volumetrically¹⁵ and a stock solution of the 0.001M concentration was prepared by appropriate dilution.

The complexing reagent, N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid (N-m-T-m-NBHA) was synthesized by the procedure described earlier¹⁶, m.p. 118° (reported 118°). The purity of the reagent was confirmed by T.L.C., I.R., and U.V. Spectra.

A 1% solution of masking agents was prepared by dissolving the requisite amount in double distilled glass water.

Procedure :

In a litre beaker, 5 ml. of a 0.001M solution of barium chloride and about 400 ml. distilled water were heated at 60° on a steambath. The 10 ml of 0.1M of N-m-Tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid in alcohol was added dropwise with constant stirring followed by 0.001M ammonium hydroxide until complete precipitation was obtained. The pH 2.5-3.0 was adjusted by ammonium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid. The solution was digested for 2.30 mins. over a steam bath, filtered through a sintered glass crucible of the porosity G4 and washed thoroughly with hot water and finally with 20% alcohol water solution (5×4 ml). The barium complex thus obtained was dried at 110° and weighed as [C₁₄H₁₁N₂O₄]₂Ba.

Separation of Barium from commonly occurring Metal Ions and Rare Earths :

With a view to separate the barium from the other commonly occurring metal ions, a 5 ml of the 0.001M solution of barium chloride was mixed with a known amount of desired foreign metal ions and diluted to 250 ml. The pH was adjusted to 2.5-3.00 as usual with 0.01M ammonium hydroxide and 0.01M hydrochloric acid. A 5 ml portion of the 1% potassium cyanide solution was added and the content was heated upto 60° on a steambath. Then, the alcoholic solution of the reagent was added dropwise to it with constant stirring. The complex so formed was allowed to stand for ½ hr, on a steambath. Thus barium could be separated and precipitated quantitatively in presence of Ag⁺, Mn⁺², Cu⁺², Ni⁺², Cd⁺², Zn⁺², Hg⁺², Pd⁺² and V⁵. Barium can also be separated and precipitated quantitatively with N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid in presence of Be⁺², Ga⁺³, Sb⁺³, As⁺³, Bi⁺³, Ti⁺⁴ and Zr⁺⁴ as above by taking 10 ml of 1% citrate and oxalate as masking agents instead of cyanide.

Likewise, barium can also be separated and precipitated quantitatively in presence of UO₂⁺² and Mo⁺⁶ using mg-EDTA as the masking agents.

For the rare earths, the barium is successfully separated and precipitated quantitatively from La⁺³, Pr⁺³, Nd⁺³ and Sm⁺³ by adjusting the pH 2.5-3.0 because all these rare earths are precipitated above the pH 3.0.

Results and Discussion

The experimental results of the present investigation are shown in Tables 1 and 2. The complex is fairly soluble in dioxane, ethanol and chloroform but sparingly soluble in ether, carbon tetrachloride and glacial acetic acid. The complex is decomposed when heated with concentrated sulphuric, nitric, hydrochloric and perchloric acids. The analytical results indicate the composition of the complex $[C_{14}H_{11}N_2O_4]_2Ba$.

TABLE 1—QUANTITATIVE DETERMINATION OF BARIUM WITH *N-m-TOLYL-m-NITROBENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID*

Barium taken mg	Barium found mg	Number of determination	Standard deviation
0.687	0.686	5	±0.01
2.061	2.059	5	±0.02
3.435	3.435	6	±0.01
4.122	4.121	5	±0.01
6.870	6.869	6	±0.02
13.740	13.740	5	±0.01

TABLE 2—SEPARATION AND GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF BARIUM FROM FOREIGN IONS

Barium taken mg	Foreign metal ions mg	Masking Agent	Barium found
6.88	Ag ⁺⁶⁰	Cyanide	6.87
4.12	Mn ⁺²¹⁰⁰	Cyanide	4.12
4.12	Ni ⁺²¹⁰⁰	Cyanide	4.13
6.88	Cu ⁺²⁸⁰	Cyanide	6.89
6.88	Zn ⁺²⁸⁰	Cyanide	6.87
6.88	Cd ⁺²⁸⁰	Cyanide	6.88
4.12	Hg ⁺²¹⁰⁰	Cyanide	4.13
4.12	Pd ⁺²⁸⁰	Cyanide	4.12
13.74	Be ⁺²¹⁰⁰	Citrate + Oxalate	13.76
13.74	Ga ⁺³⁸⁰	Citrate + Oxalate	13.75
13.74	Sb ⁺³⁸⁰	Citrate + Oxalate	13.74
6.88	As ⁺³⁸⁰	Citrate + Oxalate	6.86
6.88	Bi ⁺³⁸⁰	Citrate + Oxalate	6.87
13.74	Ti ⁺⁴⁵⁰	Citrate + Oxalate	13.74
13.74	Zr ⁺⁴⁵⁰	Citrate + Oxalate	13.75
6.88	V ^{+5 60}	Cyanide	6.89
4.12	Mo ⁺⁶¹⁰⁰	Mg-EDTA	4.13
4.12	UO ₂ ⁺²¹⁰⁰	Mg-EDTA	4.14

Analysis :

A known amount of barium complex was decomposed with a mixture of perchloric, sulphuric and nitric acid and the barium content was determined volumetrically¹⁵. The elemental analysis show the percentage composition as below :

C = 49.47%, H = 3.27%, N = 8.23%, Ba = 20.23%, and found

C = 49.48%, H = 3.26%, N = 8.25%, Ba = 20.22%

Effect of pH :

For carrying out the separation and gravimetric determination of barium in the solutions of different

pH values with all other factors identical revealed that they are irrespective at pH 2.5–3.0 range.

Masking Agents :

Experimental study shows that the presence of the excess of Mg-EDTA and cyanide did not interfere with precipitation of barium with *N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid*. However oxalate and citrate inhibited the precipitation.

Precision and Accuracy :

The present investigation for the gravimetric determination of barium has the relative average error ±0.01.

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Chemical Examination of *Hesprethusa crenulata* (Roxb) Roem.

HAFIZULLAH KHAN, S. A. SIDDIQUI & ASIF ZAMAN*

Department of Research in Unani Medicine
and

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh

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H. crenulata (N.O. Rutaceae, Hindi—Beli) grows abundantly in different parts of India. The fruit, a small globose berry, is reported to diminish intestinal fermentation, to resist the contagion of